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Vol 5:7 2026

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Abstract

It is a common experience for faith and ethics to be disconnected from the “real world” of science, technology, engineering, math and construction trades (STEM&CT). To address such challenges, I developed and facilitated a short course—known as “*The Builders Guild*”—as one component of my Doctor of Ministry thesis-project. The Builders Guild explored the integration of Biblical theology and ethical decision-making, emphasizing a Biblically transformed virtue ethic as a preferred alternative to the more commonly emphasized ethical frameworks of deontology or utilitarianism. This article surveys some of the most insightful aspects of my thesis-project. Findings suggest that integration of theology into ethics education is not only viable but deeply meaningful for practitioners who seek to resolve theological and ethical complexities inherent to vocations in STEM&CT.

Introduction and the Context of the Thesis-Project

My thesis-project explored the need and opportunity to facilitate a faith-based ethics course at a Christian ministry called “Anselm House” located at the University of Minnesota in Minneapolis. Early in the doctoral program, I intended to limit the scope of my project to practicing engineers and students enrolled in engineering programs at the University of Minnesota. While developing the thesis-project, however, I met several construction workers and technicians who expressed interest in joining a STEM-focused community of Christians. Based on my experiences as a professional engineer who is directly involved with construction projects, I am aware that engineers work closely with technicians, tradespeople, and people in various other STEM disciplines. Thus, the project scope expanded to include university students, career professionals in STEM, and practitioners representing several construction trades.

Problem Statement

It is a common experience for faith and ethics to be disconnected from the “real world” of STEM and construction trades (STEM&CT). Neil Postman uses the term “technopolies” to describe societies that are dismissive of religion and tradition and instead submit culture to the “sovereignty of technique and technology,” usually for the sake of power and progress (Postman, 1993, p. 59 & 26). Despite assumptions made by “technopolies”, customs and belief systems serve essential functions in helping people to know their history, form identity, and navigate ethical challenges. As argued by Foltz and Foltz, “To destroy belief systems is to lose the very resources needed for a meaningful democratic society” (Foltz & Foltz, 2018, p. 4). STEM education does

not escape technopoly's grip and, reflecting its very ethos, modern STEM curriculum generally exalts "technical" subjects while discounting "soft" subjects such as religion and ethics.

It is likewise not uncommon for STEM educators at Christian higher-education institutions to isolate faith from technical disciplines. After collecting and modeling surveys from 2,074 faculty representing 55 institutions from within the Council of Christian Colleges & Universities (CCCU), Kaul et al. found that: "The results of the Discipline model suggest that, on average, faculty from the field of religion and philosophy are more likely to integrate faith and learning, whereas faculty from both the hard or applied sciences and humanities are less likely to integrate their faith into the classroom" (Kaul, Hardin, & Beaujean, 2017, pp. 172–187 & 183). Jon Schmidt similarly discusses the related tendency for technical knowledge to be pursued and applied apart from ethical and social considerations: "The common perception—even among engineers—is that engineering is primarily a matter of technical problem-solving and design by solitary individuals, and that the chief function of an engineer is to devise the most efficient means to achieve an end that is specified by someone else" (Schmidt, 2013, p. 993). To isolate ethics and religious faith from daily life in STEM and the trades, however, is to grossly misunderstand the very nature of the persons and communities we claim to serve. Consequently, while practitioners in STEM and construction trades may become proficient in delivering efficient and technologically complex solutions, they are often ill-equipped to resolve theological and ethical dilemmas inherent to their work. This phenomenon is not unique to the modern classroom, however. Even seasoned professionals tend to focus narrowly on strictly technical issues while remaining unaware of—or unconcerned about—the "soft" social factors that are purportedly beyond the rigid boundaries of their profession. Whether or not people appreciate the intertwined relationship between "hard" technical topics (e.g., topics that stereotypically involve equations and schematic diagrams) and

“soft” topics (e.g., religion and ethics), such “hard” and “soft” topics are interrelated constituents that compose larger social systems and should be considered in unison rather than compartmentalized into separate spheres.

Research Questions

As an intervention to address such challenges facing STEM&CT practitioners, I designed a short course that was referred to as the “Builder’s Guild”. This course explored three common ethical frameworks (deontology, utilitarianism, and virtue ethics), with an emphasis on virtue ethics, and considered the relevance of Biblical theology in resolving complex ethical challenges within our technologically advanced and religiously diverse world. With this purpose in mind, I sought to answer the following research questions:

1. Can a properly designed course that bridges the gap between industry’s treatment of ethics and a Biblically transformed understanding of ethics lead to a robust understanding and integration of faith and ethics among people who minister in STEM and construction trades?
2. To what extent can the Builders course change perceptions regarding the role and relevance of faith and ethics in STEM and construction trades?

Introduction to Virtue Ethics

Virtue Ethics

To appreciate the emphasis on virtue ethics, it is beneficial to consider the tendency of ethics courses to focus on questions of moral permissibility (e.g., codes of conduct). Whether it be university courses or professional development modules, for example, ethics training is commonly structured to help people definitively answer legalistic questions such as “Is it ever

acceptable to take surplus materials from a construction site?” or “Can I allow people to perform tasks that they are not trained or qualified for?” or “What maximum value of ‘*gift*’ am I allowed to accept from a contractor?” Virtue ethics regards such questions as flawed because they focus on the moral permissibility of external actions rather than getting to the heart of who a person truly is (Mattison III, 2008, p. 13). The core framework of virtue ethics, rather, is for people to consider their own habits of character and introspectively consider questions such as “What kind of person ought I to *be*?” rather than focusing on legalistic questions of permissibility. Character is the core of virtue, and ethicist Alasdair MacIntyre defines virtues as “dispositions which issue in the types of action which manifest human excellence” (MacIntyre, 1998, p. 52). In *Summa theologica*, Thomas Aquinas likewise defines virtue as “a good quality of the mind, by which we live righteously, of which no one can make bad use, which God forms in us, without us” (Thomas Aquinas, n.d., p. q.55 a.4 obj. 1). NT Wright defines virtue as follows:

[Virtue] is what happens when someone has made a thousand small choices, requiring effort and concentration, to do something which is good and right but which doesn't ‘*come naturally*’—and then, on the thousand and first time, when it really matters, they find that they do what's required ‘*automatically*,’ as we say.
(Wright, 2010, p. 20)

In synthesizing wisdom contained in each of these definitions, I suggest that virtues are habituated dispositions that equip a person to act with excellence and without painstaking conscious deliberation amidst both ordinary and ethically ambiguous circumstances.

The framework of virtue ethics is outlined in Aristotle's compiled work titled *The Nicomachean Ethics*. According to Aristotle, a virtue is a character quality that, when possessed, enables a person to fulfill their function (Greek word *ergon*) with *excellence* (Greek word *arête*).

When not possessed, an absence of virtue prevents a person from functioning with excellence. Aristotle concludes that excellence is attributed to human effort and requires that people know what the human good is and actually exercise virtues that guide the pursuit of good ends (Lovin, 2011, p. 188). MacIntyre similarly explains how Aristotle determined whether or not a person was genuinely virtuous: “For Aristotle one sign of a virtuous man is that he *gets pleasure* from virtuous activity, and another is that he knows how to choose among pleasures and pains” (MacIntyre, 1998, p. 42). Thus, virtue ethics focuses on what we should *be* rather than what we should *do* and emphasizes the development of dispositions that condition habitual, stable, and predictable behaviors. Aristotle also concludes that virtues do not come naturally to anyone. Instead, virtues must be intentionally pursued and habitually exercised for a person to attain them—a person has not truly inculcated a virtue if a seemingly virtuous behavior is infrequent and “out-of-character.” In other words, virtues are *predictable* and *repeated* habits that define our character (Lovin, 2011, p. 189).

The Greek word *eudaimonia* is commonly, yet imprecisely, translated into the English word “happiness.” In *The Nicomachean Ethics*, Aristotle taught that happiness is an activity of the soul that requires complete goodness throughout a lifetime (Aristotle, 1934, p. 61 & 47 in Logos Bible Software). In contrast to modern use of the word “happiness,” Aristotle argues that happiness is not found in simple amusements and pleasantries (Aristotle, 1934, pp. 609-611 in Logos Bible Software). Nor is happiness found in wealth, fame, or power (Robinson, 2004, p. 39). Rather, Greek philosophy concludes that *eudaimonia* is about human flourishing and people fulfilling their potential through the cultivation and acquisition of virtue.

It is important to note that Aristotle was concerned with both the individual and corporate exercise of virtues. Indeed, community is the training ground—the realm where moral struggles

occur—for developing virtue. Virtues must therefore be understood in terms of how they influence dispositions and actions of individual people as well as communities. Writing from a Christian perspective, NT Wright similarly explains that Christian virtue is intended to build up the Church, so virtues must also be developed and practiced corporately within the body of Christ:

the vocation to be a royal priesthood, the challenge to develop the Christian virtues which constitute us as genuine, God-reflecting human beings, is a vocation and challenge that we receive not merely as individuals but as communities. Aristotle saw the person of virtue as taking a key role within the *polis*, the city, the basic political unit of his day. Christian virtue, though it generates great leaders, does so in order that the whole body of Christ may function with the same learned, habitual virtue. (Wright, 2010, p. 272)

Regarding how virtues are developed, Aristotle taught that a person cannot attain virtues through mere intellectual exercise. Rather, Aristotle asserts that the development of virtue requires intentionality and persistence as a person develops virtue through the process of habituation. Aristotle also believes that friendship and community are essential components of virtue development (Aristotle, 1934, pp. 461-463 in Logos Bible Software).

Analysis. Virtue ethics is holistically concerned with excellence in motivation, action (including excellence in the acquisition and application of technical knowledge!) and *actual* attainment of good ends. However, it is necessary to clarify that virtue ethics does not deem rules and consequences as irrelevant. Rules and consequences are indeed valid concerns in the broader exercise of virtue, yet rules and consequences are not themselves the penultimate consideration in virtue ethics. NT Wright similarly discusses how character development (the inculcation of

virtue) does not negate the need to either adhere to rules and/or intentionally pursue desirable ends. To the contrary, Wright explains,

Character—the transforming, shaping, and marking of a life and its habits—will generate the sort of behavior that rules might have pointed toward but which a ‘*rule-keeping*’ mentality can never achieve. And it will produce the sort of life which will in fact be true to itself—though the ‘*self*’ to which it will at last be true is the redeemed self, the transformed self, not the merely ‘*discovered*’ self of popular thought. (Wright, 2010, p. 7)

A Biblically-transformed virtue ethic complements the Christian life because of its capacity to sustain Christ-centered motivations, inform right actions, and guide a person in the pursuit of truly good ends.

Distinct Features of a Biblically Transformed Virtue Ethic

The holistic nature of virtue ethics, with its consideration of such issues as habituation, character, proper role of rules, and *telos*, renders it an appropriate framework, yet it is still lacking and in need of transformation from Biblical theology. Given the overarching argument that a Biblically transformed virtue ethic is appropriate for the ambiguous and complex nature of STEM&CT, I now highlight distinct features and applications of such a transformed framework.

Transformed Nature

One important nuance of a Biblically transformed virtue ethic concerns how we understand a person’s transformed nature. In terms of Biblical theology, Romans 6:1-11 articulates how a Christian is baptized into Christ’s death and resurrection and thereby gains a

new life in Christ. This new life in Jesus Christ involves “the Spirit’s synergistic involvement in putting to death the habits and passions of the body and progressing toward the good” (Miller & Hauerwas, 2014, p. 130). In other words, Christians live on the basis of *being* in Christ and having our sinful nature increasingly transformed into the likeness of Christ through the work of the Holy Spirit (aka “sanctification”). Expressed in various ways throughout his letters to the Church, the Apostle Paul teaches that following Jesus Christ necessarily involves exchanging sinful habits and act-based legalism for a new life in Christ. In his letter to the church in Philippi, Paul writes that the aim of life is to share in the power of the resurrection and be raised from the dead: “I want to know Christ—yes, to know the power of his resurrection and participation in his sufferings, becoming like him in his death, and so, somehow, attaining to the resurrection from the dead.”¹ Paul sought an ever-increasing knowledge of Christ, and this increasing knowledge impacted the *way* he lived. This pursuit is not unique to the Apostle Paul; no, it ought to be true of all Christians. Furthermore, Paul is not interested in moral formation for its own sake. His concern, rather, is for how Christians can best express *in action* what they have already become through faith and baptism (Harrington, SJ & Keenan, SJ, 2010, p. 110).

Actions Regulated by Our Identify

Another distinct feature of a Biblically transformed virtue ethic centers on the reality that Jesus did not come to give us a list of “do’s and don’ts” but to “confer identity upon us, and to allow us to think and act from this identity” (Brown, 2017, p. Introduction in Logos Bible Software). As stated in *Virtue Ethics*, Brad Kallenberg suggests that Aristotelian virtue ethics complements Biblical theology in that both frameworks establish an identity that informs and

¹ See Phil. 3:10-11.

regulates actions: “Christian virtue ethics analyzes moral situations relative to the *fit* of its action as measured against the character of Christ revealed in the Gospel narratives. For virtue ethics the metric is not so much effectiveness as *faithfulness to the gospel*” (Kallenberg, 2017, p. 31). In other words, God-glorifying virtues are fruit, not the cause, of our identity in Christ.

Corporate Exercise of Virtue

A third distinction centers on the corporate exercise of virtues. Similar to how Aristotle believed that virtues ought to be inculcated at both the individual and community levels, the Church itself can be considered a corporate manifestation of a virtue ethic. In Philippians 1:27, for example, Paul exhorts Christians to “conduct yourselves in a manner worthy of the gospel of Christ.” Here the English phrase “conduct yourselves” comes from translating the original Greek word *politeuomai*, which is primarily concerned with the formation of right community (*polis*) rather than being limited to the character of an individual person. In this passage, Paul exhorts Christians to emulate Christlikeness *as a community*, and this exhortation is similar in concept to Aristotle’s concern for the corporate exercise of virtues.

Biblical Paradigm of Happiness (*eudaimonia*)

Generally speaking, contemporary society often assumes that a person’s happiness is a function of accomplishments, financial wealth, and/or social status. Popular myths in STEM&CT careers likewise suggest that, for example, happiness will increase after a person finally reaches such milestones as professional licensure, secures yet another abbreviation after their last name, or manages a prestigious construction project. By implication, a person who experiences career stagnation, vocational tragedy, or even just plain “*ordinariness*” is destined to experience limited

happiness. Such myths are not unique to contemporary society, and even Aristotle argued that an otherwise virtuous person who finds himself “fallen into the direst misfortune” cannot possibly be happy amidst unfortunate circumstances (Aristotle, 1934, p. 441 in Logos Bible Software). This conditional view of happiness is poignantly refuted in a book titled *The cross before me: reimagining the way to the good life*, in which the authors explore the “cruciform way” of life. The overarching thesis of this book is that “Happiness is communion with God. And the way to communion with God is the *way of the cross*” (Wilbourne & Gregor, 2019, p. Ch. 9 in Logos Bible Software). By implication, humans—who are, in fact, image-bearers of God—cannot experience true happiness apart from a restored relationship with their Creator. The “cruciform way,” as discussed by Wilbourne and Gregor, centers on how Jesus’ suffering and death on the cross brings salvation and establishes the *ordinary* way of life for Christians.² During Christ’s incarnate life, death, and resurrection, Jesus fully and perfectly demonstrated what it means to live as a true image-bearer of God.³ Jesus’s life therefore exemplifies the nature of a truly “good life,” which involves such virtues as humility and sacrificial love and rejection of the world’s empty promises and notions of happiness apart from God. From a Biblical perspective, contemporary society’s misconceptions about happiness ought to be of comparatively little concern to a Christian. Indeed, our inattention to Kingdom realities is the primary barrier that inhibits true happiness. Furthermore, a Christian who is overly concerned with his or her own temporal fortune or worldly pleasures functionally glorifies self above God—this is idolatry. We find life and true happiness, rather, when we commune with Christ.⁴

² See Matt 16:24-28.

³ See Gen 1:27 and Col 1:15.

⁴ See Matt 10:32-39.

Christ-centered *telos*

Another noteworthy difference between Greek philosophy and Biblical theology centers on what each paradigm considers the penultimate purpose of individual people and communities. The Greek word *telos* refers to ultimate purpose or function, and it is readily observed that questions of *telos* are at the forefront of peoples' minds. For example, we commonly encounter questions to the tone of, "What is the purpose of life?" or "What job best aligns with my goals?". As just one reflection of such concerns, a journal article titled "*A thematic analysis of Tweets about purpose in life,*" concludes that people often believe it is possible to discover their purpose in life, but the burden of searching for life purpose is itself a source of much anxiety (Bronk, Cheung, Mehoke, & Pham, 2023, pp. 674-687). Conveniently—but rarely in a person's genuine best interest—our cultural liturgies are quick to provide self-serving (and sometimes obscure!) answers to questions of *telos*.

From a Biblical perspective, the *telos* of God's image-bearers is demonstrated in the incarnate life of Jesus Christ. As God's image-bearers, our primary *telos* is to repent, love and submit to the lordship of Jesus Christ, and seek to bring glory to God. Reinforcing this *telos*, Augustine began his *Confessions* by emphasizing that humans are made for the purpose of knowing and worshiping God. In the English translation of the *Confessions* we read of the human *telos*: "To praise Thee is the wish of man who is but a part of Thy creation. Thou dost bestir him so that he takes delight in praising Thee: *for Thou hast made us for Thee and our heart is unquiet till it finds its rest in Thee*" (Augustine of Hippo, 1953, p. 1.1.1). In another commonly recited text, Question #1 of the Westminster Shorter Catechism famously communicates a God-oriented *telos* in the statement that "the chief end of man is to glorify God and enjoy Him forever" (The Westminster shorter catechism: with Scripture proofs, 1996).

Needless to say, the Biblical *telos* is quite different from propositions of *telos* as prescribed by contemporary society. In fact, the Biblical *telos* perhaps even contradicts much of mainstream Christianity, which often teaches—implicitly if not explicitly—that a person’s penultimate *telos* is simply a matter of escaping hell. The foremost concern of Biblical theology, rather, is *the glory of God*, and our individual salvation is a participatory history in that glory.

In addition to considering the *telos* of the individual person, we must also consider the *telos* of community and the *polis*. The *telos* of community is pertinent because people are, of course, significantly shaped by the communities in which they live. From the vantagepoint of Biblical theology, the *telos* of the community of Believers is to fulfill our calling as the body of Christ. The body of Christ, to be clear, is an eschatological community of people who have been reconciled with God and embody “their experience of God’s salvation in their relations with each other” (Wall, 1992, p. 1103). Such relationships, as well as corporate stewardship of God-given gifts, edify people within and outside the community and provide tangible witness to all. Similar to how a person’s individual salvation is a participatory history of God’s glory, the Church (*ekklesia*) is a participatory corporate manifestation of the Kingdom of God.

Humility and Virtuous Suffering

Two unique features of a Biblically transformed virtue ethic are the interrelated virtues of humility and virtuous suffering. Humility and virtuous suffering are certainly not regarded as virtues according to Greek philosophy, and contemporary ethics textbooks heavily reflect the Greek view by remaining silent on these topics. In fact, none of the ethics textbooks I acquired when preparing for the *Builders* course contained discussion on suffering, and humility was only scarcely mentioned. I speculate that the notable quietness on suffering and humility is likely

attributed to the fact that suffering and humility are taboo topics within high-modernist technopolies wherein each individual person carries the burden of creating themselves and building their own success. In such a worldview, the experience of suffering is functionally regarded as a well-deserved consequence of weakness and/or an accurate reflection of a person's own inadequacies and failures. Needless to say, this paradigm leaves many casualties mercilessly strewn along the wayside. Given our current cultural moment, it is timely and beneficial to contemplate a Biblical understanding of humility and virtuous suffering.

Humility. The virtue of humility is a prominent attribute of Jesus Christ, and Jesus explicitly exhorted his followers to learn humility from him.⁵ Jesus demonstrated humility through such things as washing his disciples' feet, eating with sinners, and ultimately humbling himself to death on a cross. The prescribed and exemplified virtue of humility starkly contradicts Greek philosophy's exaltation of *megalopsychia*, which asserts that a virtuous person ought to know their own purported greatness and pursue great things for their own honor. Contrasting the Greek and contemporary worldviews, humility is a uniquely Biblical disposition that shifts focus away from self (Robinson, 2004, p. 47). Pertaining to the relevance of humility in STEM&CT vocations, we do our work as unto the Lord and thereby *not* primarily for financial gain, career advancement, or numerous other forms of praise and personal benefit. Wilbourne and Gregor write that "humility aspires to do excellent work, that it might be a blessing to others, that it might be life-giving. And in those times when our work turns out as somewhat less than we'd hoped, humility accepts that with joy as well" (Wilbourne & Gregor, 2019, p. Ch. 4 in Logos Bible Software).

⁵ See Matt 11:29.

Virtuous suffering. Closely related to humility is the concept of virtuous suffering. Regardless of any reasons why humility and suffering are largely absent from ethics textbooks, suffering is an inevitable experience and therefore remains an incredibly relevant discussion topic. For example, STEM&CT practitioners who steward their vocations well will hopefully reduce suffering through such contributions as providing water and wastewater treatment, developing medicines, designing and constructing structurally sound buildings, or developing technologies that enhance food security. As one incredibly complex example from our current cultural moment, attempts are being made to develop Artificial Intelligence and transhumanism for the purpose of eliminating human work and physical suffering altogether—this presents a slew of ethical and theological questions for which we must prepare to respond.

As we lessen the sufferings of other people, STEM&CT practitioners may also suffer themselves while toiling within a dishonest and otherwise sinful world. As just a few representative examples, people may suffer termination or demotion if they are honest about design errors or fraud, publish unpopular research findings, or pursue accountability for shoddy work. Such consequences may rightly be categorized as “virtuous suffering.” In societies that idolize comfort and pleasure, however, virtuous suffering is counter-cultural and perhaps even absurd. Whether our sufferings are significant or small, however, the Bible exhorts us to “rejoice in our sufferings, knowing that suffering produces endurance, and endurance produces character, and character produces hope, and hope does not put us to shame, because God's love has been poured into our hearts through the Holy Spirit who has been given to us.”⁶ Since suffering is an inevitable experience for every person, it remains an incredibly relevant topic for *Builders* to contemplate from the vantagepoint of Biblical theology.

⁶ See Rom 5:3-5.

Developing Virtue Through Intentional Habituation and Submission to the Holy Spirit

Another distinguishing feature of a Biblically transformed virtue ethic is recognition that virtues are developed both by the Holy Spirit and through the countless and seemingly trivial decisions that form our everyday habits. Concerning the Christian life, the Holy Spirit does not usually free us from sinful habits in a single moment. Rather, it seems that the *modus operandi* of the Holy Spirit is to convict a person of sin, lead them to repentance, and cause the person to yield to the Holy Spirit throughout the lifelong process of sanctification. For example, in 2 Peter 1:5-11 we see the development of Christian virtue as a *process* rather than an instantaneous work of the Holy Spirit. Christians who exhibit little concern for putting off the old self and renewing their minds, assuming that God will simply refine their character as He sees fit,⁷ functionally replicate the logic of the wicked servant who hid his master's money rather than exert reasonable effort to invest it.⁸ In other words, there is a mysterious and legitimate role for people to take practical actions, make decisions, and cooperate with the Holy Spirit as we follow Christ.

⁷ See Eph 4:17-24.

⁸ See Matt 25:14-30.

Thesis-Project Design

The previous discussion presented some of the core concepts that I discussed in module #3 of the *Builders Guild*, which was the highlight of the course. The *Builders Guild* was hosted at Anselm House, which is a Christian ministry located on the University of Minnesota campus. Anselm House offers lectures, fellowships, and short courses designed to integrate faith and life, making it an ideal setting for this study. The following discussion highlights the design and findings from the course.

Population and Sample Size

The course cohort consisted of participants from engineering, construction, and other STEM-related fields. These individuals represented diverse technical and vocational backgrounds, enabling rich dialogue and comparative analysis. Eight active participants attended all three modules. Five active participants attended two modules, and one active participant attended only one module. Some participants either registered but didn't attend the course or attended without registering; these participants were not regarded as "active participants" and their data was not included in the study.

Table 1 summarizes active participants' vocation and perceived level of knowledge about ethics before the *Builders* course commenced. In the pre-course survey, eight active participants had "no" to "some" knowledge, and six participants believed they had "moderate" to "expert" knowledge of ethics.

Table 1*Active participant vocations and pre-course knowledge of ethics*

Participant #	STEM or a Trade	Declared academic and/or career discipline	PRE-COURSE SURVEY QUESTION#6: What is your existing (pre-course) level of knowledge about common ethical frameworks?
Participant #001	STEM	Physics degree, finance career	Moderate knowledgeable
Participant #002	STEM	Mechanical Engineering	Some knowledge
Participant #003	TRADE	Fabrication	Some knowledge
Participant #004	TRADE	Construction	Moderate knowledgeable
Participant #005	STEM	Biomedical Engineering	Moderate knowledgeable
Participant #006	STEM	Organization Development and Quality/Process Improvement (including applied statistics)	Expert knowledge
Participant #007	STEM	Sr Engineer (M.E.)	No knowledge
Participant #009	STEM	Project Manager	Moderate knowledgeable
Participant #010	STEM	Civil Engineering	Some knowledge
Participant #011	STEM	Philology and technology	Slight knowledge
Participant #012	OTHER	Ed Psychology-Special Education and Applied Behavior Analysis	Slight knowledge
Participant #013	STEM	Information and operational technology	Some knowledge
Participant #015	STEM	Engineering	Slight knowledge
Participant #016	TRADE	Inventor	Moderate knowledgeable

The course consisted of three modules. The first module explored the merits and deficiencies of deontology and utilitarianism, and ways that Biblical theology may transform these frameworks. The second module explored the merits and deficiencies of strict Aristotelean virtue ethics, and ways that Biblical theology may transform the Greek cardinal virtues of courage, temperance, justice, prudence. The third module, which is the focus of this article, explored the merits and deficiencies of a Biblically transformed virtue ethic with emphasis on the theological virtues of faith, hope, and love.

Procedures of Data Collection and Analysis

My thesis-project utilized an exploratory mixed-methods methodology. Data collection instruments included pre- and post-course surveys, transcripts of in-class meeting discussions, and written data from one-minute papers. These data collection instruments were mostly qualitative in nature, and I evaluated data to determine the extent to which course outcomes and objectives were achieved. Data analysis involved identifying recurring themes, shifts in perception, and qualitative reflections from participants that evidenced increased understanding and integration of theological ethics.

Validity, Reliability, Generalizability, Transferability, and Replicability

Triangulation of surveys, recorded transcripts of the in-class discussions, and written reflections helped ensure internal validity. Reliability was strengthened through consistent facilitation of the course, consistency in questions in the pre- and post-course surveys, and structured writing exercises. While the study's faith-based context limits its generalizability to secular audiences, its transferability to other Christian ministries is strong. The course curriculum, methodology, and findings may be replicated in other faith-based vocational and international education contexts with appropriate adaptation.

Project Findings

I used recorded transcripts of the in-class meeting, pre- and post- course surveys to assess how effective the course was in terms of changing participants' attitudes about ethics, increasing the level of confidence that participants have in terms of integrating faith and ethics in their vocations, evaluating whether course participants gained an appreciation for the sacred nature of their vocation, and determining potential shifts in how participants understand and appreciate the

relevance of ethics and theology to their vocations. Data suggests that participants valued the course's introduction to ethical frameworks and especially appreciated the theological depth and personal relevance of the Biblically transformed virtue ethic.

Recorded Transcripts from Module #3

A thematic analysis was conducted of each recorded transcript. Results of Module #3, which focused on a Biblically transformed virtue ethic, is discussed in the following section.

Thematic Analysis of Course Discussions

In Module #3, participants explored the theological virtues of faith, hope and love.

Faith. Participants #001, #003, #004, #006, #007, #010, and #011 engaged in a discussion on faith. These participants largely concluded that faith, depending upon context, is characterized by trusting in your own beliefs, the beliefs of others, and ultimately in God. It was also suggested that faith relates to courage, faith involves an element of curiosity and truth-seeking, and faith requires humility. Regarding courage, participants felt that the practical application of faith in the real world requires courage to ask questions. Ultimately faith was characterized by trust, courage, humility, and strength. The following quote from Participant #011 reflects the broader discussion:

When it came to faith, it was a question of—do you trust your methodology and your experience and all the observations that you have made, such as the age of the house? The way [the house] was built and so forth, versus blindly trusting technology and a procedure that may have been designed for a more recent way of building things. Do you just trust whatever the paper says, or do you go through and have the faith to be able to

say, *'No, I see it differently. Here's how I'm going to mark it'*? Even though your boss said, *'No, the first three [people] marked it right.'*

There was consensus that faith permeates STEM and construction trades, and this is exemplified by the necessity to trust the integrity of technical reports, co-workers, and quality of the materials we use and produce. Participant #006 shared the following anecdote from his own life:

I recently had some remodeling done and worked with an electrician. When it came time for the inspection, the inspector looked around a little bit, saw the electrician's name on the box, and he said, *'It's all good.'* Why? *'Because I know his [the contractor's] work.'* The benefit of being a faithful person senses of the word...I may have nuanced it a bit. He looked around first and then he looked *who* did the work, and knew that he wouldn't have to check further, because in this case the appearances aligned with the things he couldn't see, because of the people he knew who did it. Back to your point [to participant #011], you don't have to check everything yourself. At some point you've got to trust, and I can tell you other stories where I wish I could tear the wall apart because I'm sure they didn't do it right.

Hope. The next theological virtue of discussion was hope. Hope received less discussion than either faith or love. However, participants shared insightful thoughts regarding the application of hope as a theological virtue in everyday life. Participants found hope to be less clearly defined than faith, with more divergent views on the definition of hope and its application to STEM and the trades. Hope was considered by some participants to present the risk of naive or manufactured hope. Some participants found hope in the workplace to be multifaceted, meaning

there might be divergent applications of hope across professional disciplines. For example, hope was felt to be absent in certain professions (e.g., lawyers), and this type of hope was juxtaposed to uniquely Christian hope. Participant #003 stated:

There's different kind of bounds in which hope operates where you can have hope in your coworkers, you can have hope in the goals of your company or the goals of your team, or frankly, the goals of your profession. We [the participant's breakout group] talked about law and being a lawyer that there are bounds in which you can have this real sense of hope in a legal system, let's say. Then we also touched on how this ultimate hope is a uniquely Christian ultimate hope that is not shaken by the reality that the things that we hope in often fail. There's a uniquely Christian element of this ultimate hope that is an odd thing to the rest of the world.

Love. As the third virtue of consideration, participants engaged in discussions on love. When considering love as a theological virtue that applies to everyday life, participants suggested that STEM disciplines are prone to desensitizing or otherwise dehumanizing people. It was perceived that people are often treated as “resources” rather than with dignity as true *imago Dei* beings. In many situations, there is little concern or demonstrable love for people. One notable statement from Participant #005 included:

Because the example given, the case study was treating people as ‘resources’. The kind of language that we use when we say people are ‘resources,’ specifically it talks about on the other side of the world, there's a family, when I see the leadership in my company getting the wrong picture about this developer group and then treating them like trash or treat the employees like commodities and even the language we use. What I was saying is

people are our greatest resource anywhere that you go, but people don't stop there. They're more than '*resources*.'

On a positive note, however, it was suggested that love may be a growing force in STEM. Participants suggested that love is demonstrated through a growing emphasis on the social and environmental impacts of things we produce. This was also considered the case given that the virtue of love can be a catalyst to improve the quality of our work. Participant #009 explained:

It's just interesting to see how the World Bank is asking for environmental and social impact assessments to be done and safeguards to be put in place on different projects. I've seen projects being stopped because their worker got injured or there's a fatality on the construction site. Whereas in previous years, environmental impact assessments were not really an in-thing. It's only in recent years, globally. I thought to your last point, that it's interesting how it's coming in, in the name of the environment and social impact. I think probably the driving force behind it could be love.

Overall, participants seemed more comfortable and confident exploring the theological virtues of faith and hope compared to discussing the virtue of love. There was common agreement about what faith means as a theological virtue. Participants had less agreement about love, perhaps indicating less knowledge, comfort, or understanding of how love relates to vocations in STEM and the trades.

Analysis of Pre-Course and Post-Course Surveys

Participants were asked in the pre- and post-course surveys to identify whether the *Builders Guild* would increase their desire to integrate their faith into their work. Pre- and post-

course survey data indicate an overall increase in participants' desire to integrate faith and work after the course, but I am reluctant to draw firm conclusions about whether these results can be attributed to the *Builders* course itself. After all, course participants likely already had a desire to integrate faith and work before registering for the course.

When asked whether their expectations about the course were met, participants had varying responses. A common theme among participants was that they expected the *Builders* course to more deeply explore specific issues in their specific contexts. A related theme was that participants were grateful for the broad focus and introduction to virtue ethics. Aside from these themes, survey data indicates that participants may not have had clear expectations about the course or they had trouble articulating these expectations when completing the survey.

When asked whether participation in the course increased their knowledge of ethical frameworks, responses were largely united in the pre- and post-course surveys. Of pre-course survey responses, 93% (N=13) expressed some form of agreement in the expectation that the course would increase participants' knowledge of ethical frameworks. Post-course surveys confirmed that this objective was accomplished, with 100% of participants agreeing to the following statement: "*The 'Builders' course increased my knowledge of ethical frameworks.*" While post-course survey responses were unanimous on this question, three participants had a slight decrease in their level of agreement with this question when compared to their pre-course answers. Participant #006 downgraded from "Agree" in the pre-course survey to "Somewhat agree" in the post-course survey, writing "good to see Dave's approach (the written materials), hear him talk about it (your examples are great), and listen to how others understand and apply the concepts and models." Participant #006's comment is not negative, however, and this person still agreed that the course increased their knowledge.

Participants were largely united in their responses when asked if they felt the *Builders* course increased their confidence and ability to integrate faith into ethical decision-making. In the post-course survey, thirteen participants expressed some level of agreement, and one participant disagreed with the statement that “*this course increased my confidence and ability to integrate faith as I resolve ethical challenges at work.*” Participant #011 disagreed with this survey question and commented, “what I’m missing is how my religious faith impacts my interaction with all ethical frameworks and how I can translate my religious beliefs about the world and my duty toward others into language that can be understood by others not sharing my religious beliefs.” This concern could be resolved in the future by providing additional course Modules that invite practitioners in STEM and construction trades to explore such issues in another student-centered class.

In terms of how the content of the *Builders* course might apply to daily life, one theme that emerged in the survey data is that participants believed the course would help them interact and communicate with other people. Some participants also indicated that the course made them more aware of specific virtues they could focus on at work. When asked about the highlight of the course, participants expressed appreciation for group discussions and opportunities to meet and talk with each other. Indicative of this appreciation, participant #005 wrote, “meeting people and exchanging their work stories.”

One value of the course is that it exposed participants to the types of ethical issues they may encounter in the future. For example, participant #003 wrote, “I realized that as I advance in my career, the moral/ethical weight of my decisions will increase,” and participant #012 wrote, “I learnt about the virtues of prudence, love and hope. I work with people with disabilities and their families. [This] course will be relevant to how I relate and work with my clients or students

and their families.” Other participants expressed similar sentiments. Overall, participants enjoyed the fledgling friendships and hearing stories from each other’s lives.

Recommendations for Future Research

Future research should explore long-term behavioral outcomes for *Builders Guild* alumni, potentially comparing faith-integrated approaches to secular ethics training. Replication at other Christian colleges, trade schools, workplace settings, and in cross-cultural contexts would provide additional insights regarding impact and scalability.

Future courses should also invite participants to share ethical dilemmas they face in their respective vocations. During the Builders course, I facilitated a fictional, though representative, case study in Module #1. In Modules #2 and #3, I invited course participants to consider the ethical challenges described during my pre-thesis interviews. To make future courses even more relevant, before the course it may be beneficial for me to invite course participants to partake in an interview or write a short narrative regarding an ethical challenge they have personally experienced or witnessed in their workplace. These scenarios could then be explored in-depth during class discussions. Research is needed to determine the impacts of such an approach in making courses even more relevant and impactful to participants.

Finally, I intend to adapt the course to facilitate interfaith dialogue and explore virtues of other religions and worldviews, hopefully in international contexts. Revisiting the original ambition of developing an ethics curriculum for technological universities in Myanmar, for example, this thesis-project advanced knowledge that may help me to develop future courses that enhance religious literacy, foster interfaith dialogue, and explore ethical decision-making in cross-cultural contexts. While this thesis-project focused primarily on how virtue ethics and

Biblical theology inform ethical decision-making, I am interested in designing future trainings that have an interreligious dialogue component.

Conclusion

The *Builders Guild* fostered ethical reflections rooted in Biblical theology. Theologically grounded virtue ethics proved not only intellectually robust but also practical and spiritually formative among practitioners in STEM and construction trades. Findings from this project also suggest that faith-integrated ethics education can prepare professionals in technical fields to navigate ethical challenges with theological integrity. Participants developed deeper commitments to Biblical virtues and gained practical perspectives to be faithfully present in their vocations, reinforcing that engineering and technical education needs to engage moral formation and not simply rule compliance. This project also affirms that faithful presence requires a reimagining of how ethics education is delivered—one where people take an integrated approach in surveying Biblical theology and ethical frameworks while having honest conversations about the messiness of real life.

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